

Chalcones X: Syntheses of Naphthalene Chalcone Analogues

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A number of naphthalene analogues of chalcone have been synthesised to study their antimicrobial activity against gram positive (*S. aureus*) and gram negative (*E. coli*) bacteria¹⁻⁵. They were synthesised through the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone and aryl aldehydes² in presence of alcoholic potash to yield the naphthyl styryl ketones. The condensation with chloro- and methoxy-benzaldehydes were effected at room temperature for 6-8 hrs, for methyl-benzaldehydes at room temperature for 30-50 hrs; and for the hydroxy benzaldehydes in cold for 7 days. The compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

The compounds gave crystalline orange to red 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, and vivid colours on melting with concentrated sulphuric acid. Elemental analyses of C, H and N for the ketones and the dinitrophenylhydrazones were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the expected value.

The results of antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* were not encouraging.

TABLE I

R	M.P. °C* of		Yield %	Halochromism with conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Analyses
	Chalcone	2 : 4-DNP			
3-OH	211	255	36	brown	C,H,N
2-Cl	176	—	87	crimson red	C,H
3-Cl	121	258	81	blood-red	C,H,N
4-Cl	138	267 (dec)	85	blood-red	C,H,N
2-Me	176	268	63	orange	C,H,N
3-Me	88	241	57	pink	C,H,N
4-Me	133	—	60	chocolate	C,H
2-MeO	122	252	62	purple	C,H,N
3-MeO	138	262	55	brown	C,H,N
3-MeO-4-OH-5-Br	131	—	57	orange	C,H
2,3-(MeO) ₂	144	208	64	brown	C,H,N
3,4-(MeO) ₂	148	233	66	violet	C,H,N
4-NMe ₂	93	—	54	blood-red	C,H
2-OH-5,6-benzo	81	217	38	purple	C,H,N

* All melting points are uncorrected. Crystallised from ethyl acetate.

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